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San Vicente, Tarlac City, Philippines, 2300

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Breaking The Barrier: Persons With Disabilities (PWDs) As A Workforce in The Philippines

Billy Jay N. Pedron, PTRP, Ph.D

Professor

De La Salle Medical and Health Sciences Institute

Executive Summary

This Policy Brief discusses the pressing unemployment problem among Persons with Disabilities in our country. There are roughly 1.44 million Filipinos who are living with disability in the Philippines, and most are living in poverty. There is a link between employment and poverty, where unemployment lies at the center of the poverty cycle. PWDs, like any other individuals, could perform their work-related tasks. Some even overperformed compared to their abled counterparts. As a result, there are gains in hiring PWDs for the institution and our country.

Years have passed after the enactment of R.A. No. 7277, also known as the Magna Carta for Persons with Disabilities. However, PWDs still face challenges, particularly in getting decent jobs to improve their quality of life. Problems include job matching, insufficient work in private institutions, and reintegration problems.

Problem Statement

Community integration for persons with disabilities (PWDs) is society's overall goal toward inclusivity. Community Integration enables PWDs to participate fully in society, the same as non-disabled individuals. It also allows them to contribute their skills and talent to the community despite their disability. One area of community integration is through employment. Employment allows PWDs to access essential commodities and support their medical expenses through their monthly salary.

Further, hiring PWDs can also help the government cut the cost of its financial subsidy to PWDs and better allocate its funds to many more affected individuals. Unfortunately, despite numerous bills and policies drafted and created to address the gap in hiring employees with disabilities, PWDs still experience difficulty being employed and getting equal working opportunities compared to non-disabled individuals.

Review of Related Literature

Globally, around 1.3 billion individuals are estimated to suffer from disability (WHO, 2023). Disability ranges from physical to psychological that can affect various age groups. The rates of disability are higher in groups with low educational attainment and higher incidence in

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females than men (United Nations, n.d). Moreover, most PWDs live in developing countries, and people with the poorest classification have a disability (United Nations, n.d). For example, in the Philippines, based on the 2010 census, out of 92.1 million individuals, there were around 1.44 million living with a disability (PSA, n.d). Disability is highest in Region IV-A, with more males affected than females, and highest among the 5 to 19 age group. Further, in the 2016 National Disability Prevalence Survey, it can be noted that 12 percent of Filipinos suffered severe disability

Persons with disabilities belong to the vulnerable sector that faces barriers and inequalities. According to World Report on Disability (2011), PWDs are denied equal opportunities and access to education, health, political participation, and employment. In addition, exclusion and discrimination were also rampant due to their impairment and socio- demographic background. Every day, PWDs are challenged by various barriers in performing their activity of daily living. According to the Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (2020), barriers make it difficult for a PWD to function or participate in society.

Community integration is the solution to break the barrier of stigma amongst PWDs. Integration ensures access to the community's education, health, employment, and other opportunities. Employment is one aspect of integration that needs to be addressed. According to the International Labour Organization (2023), employment of PWDs in both government and private sectors is low due to various barriers in hiring. In the U.S., the type of disability, insufficient education or training, the accessibility adjustment in the workplace, and lack of PWD-friendly transportation were among the barriers reported. In addition, employed PWDs are having trouble performing their work mainly because of their disability (U.S. Bureau of Labor Statistics, 2022). In the study of Mina (2017), the low employment outcomes in our country can be attributed to low education and lack of training, limited employment opportunities, physical barriers, and low awareness of relevant policies and programs.

There are benefits to hiring PWD in our country. According to U.N.- Economic and Social Commission for Asia and the Pacific, countries could increase their by 1 and 7 percent of their GDP if the salary of PWDs is the same as their co-workers. In addition, access to employment can help PWD increase their opportunity, escape poverty, and have a better quality of life. PWDs have the talent and skills to become productive at work. A study by Seva (2020) found that the productivity of PWDs is comparable with other employees.

Critique of Policy Options

Republic Act No. 7277

R. A No. 7277, also known as the Magna Carta for Disabled Persons and Other Purposes. This act allows PWD to be reintegrated into society through rehabilitation, self-development, and self-reliance. Employment of PWDs is protected and taken into consideration under this act. Some provisions provide equal opportunity for employment, sheltered employment, apprenticeship, incentives for employers, vocational rehabilitation, and counseling.

The following are the identified issues regarding the implementation of R.A No. 7277

1. The job matching gap between the skill set of PWDs and the available job in the market is the primary problem faced by PWDs. Although the act directs government

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agencies to establish vocational rehabilitation and counseling programs, it cannot confer with the demands of the industry. Based on the existing programs, cooking, baking, and massage are the regular training for PWDs to enroll in. However, using the principle of vocational rehabilitation, the training should be aligned with the market's demands. In addition, based on my experience working in the community, limited LGUs offer vocational rehabilitation and perform job placement.

2. Private institutions are not mandated by the law to hire PWDs. Instead, the law only encourages private institutions to hire and employ PWDs with an incentive.
3. The law does protect an individual who suffered an accident or medical condition that makes them disabled to reintegrate back to work after rehabilitation.

Policy Recommendation

1. It should be included in the Implementing Rules and Regulation of RA 7277 to create a working group that includes various government agencies and private institutions to evaluate the market's needs and demands. In addition, it will guide what training will be created and offered to the PWDs. At the local government level, an inter-agency unit should also be included that will identify, provide training and skills, and do job placement activities. Based on experience, the Persons with Disability Affairs Office is responsible for the welfare of PWDs. However, due to a limited budget, functions, and activities pertaining to reintegration to work are not adequately addressed.
2. In order to promote workplace inclusivity for both government and private institutions, the law should mandate institutions to hire and employ PWDs at least 1% of the workers. This will ensure that companies and institutions across fields create jobs for PWDs. Disability Welfare Office should be created in every company to check the welfare of PWD while working. In addition, the personnel in the disability welfare office should have disability sensitivity training to avoid bias in hiring an individual and can handle PWD applicants.
3. Disability can be permanent or temporary based on the condition of an individual. Therefore, there should be a provision in the law that provides an option for an employee to resign from work or transfer to another office provided, despite disability, that they can still perform another work-related task. In that way, an employee can continue working

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